

A NEW EQUATION FOR STRONG ELECTROLYTES. PART II

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The new equation for uni-univalent strong electrolytes has been generalised for any binary electrolyte.

In a previous communication (this *issue*, p. 199), an equation has been derived for univalent strong electrolyte. In this paper the equation has been generalised for any binary electrolyte, $X_\mu Y_\nu$. Moreover, the restriction imposed therein under assumption (1) has been removed. The number of positive and negative ions per unit volume around a central ion is given not by Boltzmann's distribution but by an analogous Fermi-Dirac distribution (cf. Dutta and Bagchi, *Indian J. Phys.*, 1950, 24, 66) wherein the proportionality constant is taken to be equal to the total number of ions present, since the potential in any solution of the electrolyte presumably depends on all the ions present.

The distribution is then given by

$$\left. \begin{aligned} n_+ &= \frac{N}{A_+ e^{Z_+ \lambda} + 1} \\ n_- &= \frac{N}{A_- e^{-Z_- \lambda} + 1} \end{aligned} \right\} \dots (1)$$

where N is the total number of ions present per unit volume and n_+ and n_- are the number of positive and negative ions per unit volume.

Z_+ and Z_- are the valencies of positive and negative ions; A_+ and A_- are the constants to be determined. $\lambda = e\psi/kT$; ψ = the potential at any point around a central ion; e, k, T have their usual significances.

Consider a central positive ion of valency Z_+ at a concentration (molar) C of the electrolyte $X_\mu Y_\nu$. At a distance where there is no field *i.e.*, where $\psi \rightarrow 0$, the number of positive ions is μC and that of negative ions is νC

$$\text{Hence } n_+ = \frac{(\mu + \nu) C}{A_+ + 1} = \mu C$$

$$\text{or } A_+ = \frac{\nu}{\mu} = \frac{Z_-}{Z_+}$$

$$\text{Similarly, } A_- = \frac{Z_-}{Z_+}$$

... (2)

Therefore the charge density

$$\begin{aligned} \rho &= Ne \left[\frac{Z_+}{\frac{Z_+}{Z_-} e^{Z_+ \lambda} + 1} - \frac{Z_-}{\frac{Z_-}{Z_+} e^{-Z_- \lambda} + 1} \right] \\ &= Ne Z_+ Z_- \left[\frac{1}{Z_+ e^{Z_+ \lambda} + 1} - \frac{1}{Z_- e^{-Z_- \lambda} + 1} \right] \end{aligned}$$

Now for $\lambda \rightarrow 0$

$$\rho \approx -NeZ_+Z_- \frac{(Z_+^2 + Z_-^2)}{(Z_+ + Z_-)^2} \lambda$$

and for $\lambda \rightarrow \infty$

$$\rho \approx -NeZ_-$$

Hence Poisson's equation gives

$$\nabla^2 \psi = - \frac{4\pi}{D} \rho$$

which for $\lambda \rightarrow 0$ reduces to

$$\nabla^2 \lambda = \frac{4\pi Ne^2 Z_+ Z_- (Z_+^2 + Z_-^2)}{DkT(Z_+ + Z_-)^2} \lambda = K^2 \lambda \quad \dots \text{ (II)}$$

and for $\lambda \rightarrow \infty$ to

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla^2 \lambda &= \frac{4\pi Ne^2 Z_-}{DkT} \\ &= \frac{4\pi Ne^2 Z_+ Z_- (Z_+^2 + Z_-^2)}{DkT(Z_+ + Z_-)^2} \cdot \frac{(Z_+ + Z_-)^2}{Z_+ (Z_+^2 + Z_-^2)} \\ &= K^2 m_+ \quad \dots \text{ (III)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\left. \begin{aligned} K^2 &= \frac{4\pi Ne^2 Z_+ Z_- (Z_+^2 + Z_-^2)}{DkT(Z_+ + Z_-)^2} \\ m_+ &= \frac{(Z_+ + Z_-)^2}{Z_+ (Z_+^2 + Z_-^2)} \end{aligned} \right\} \dots \text{ (3)}$$

Now, proceeding as before and fitting the curves of the two equations (II) and (III) at $\lambda = m_+$ we get finally

$$\ln f_+ = \frac{m_+}{2} \left[K^2 a_+^2 + P + \phi(g) + \sum_i n_i \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial n_i} \right] \quad \dots \text{ (4)}$$

where a_+ is the effective ionic radius of the central ion

$$\left. \begin{aligned} P &= \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} \tan^{-1} \sqrt{3} - \frac{1}{2} \ln 3 \\ \phi(g) &= \frac{1}{2} \ln \{ (1+g)^{2/3} + (1+g)^{1/3} + 1 \} - \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} \tan^{-1} \frac{2(1+g)^{1/3} + 1}{\sqrt{3}} - \frac{1}{2} (1+g)^{2/3} \\ \sum_i n_i \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial n_i} &= \frac{1}{2} \frac{\frac{h}{(1+g)^{1/3}} + \frac{h}{2(1+g)^{2/3}}}{(1+g)^{2/3} + (1+g)^{1/3} + 1} - \frac{h}{3(1+g)^{2/3} \{ 1 + \frac{1}{3} [2(1+g)^{1/3} + 1]^2 \}} - \frac{h}{2(1+g)^{2/3}} \end{aligned} \right\} \text{ (4a)}$$

$$\begin{aligned} h &= \frac{Z_+ e^2 K}{m_+ DkT} + K^2 a_+^2 \\ g &= \frac{3Z_+ e^2 K}{m_+ DkT} + K^2 a_+^2 \end{aligned}$$

Hence the mean activity coefficient, $f_{\pm}$, of the electrolyte is given by

$$\ln f_{\pm} = \frac{Z_- \ln f_+ + Z_+ \ln f_-}{Z_+ + Z_-} \quad \dots (5)$$

It will be noted that all the above equations are reduced to the corresponding equations for uni-univalent electrolytes given in the previous communication.

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

Tables I, II and Figs. 1 and 2 give the observed (in the molal scale of concentration) and calculated (in the molar scale of concentration) values of activity coefficient of KCl and CsCl. The columns I, II and III refer to the values of activity coefficients calculated respectively from Debye's equation $\nabla^2\lambda = K^2\lambda$ (I)

where $K^2 = \frac{4\pi e^2}{DkT} \sum n_i Z_i^2$ and from equations

$\nabla^2\lambda = K^2\lambda$ (II) and $\nabla^2\lambda = K^2 m_+$ (III)

where $K_2^2 = \frac{4\pi N e^2 Z_+ Z_- (Z_+^2 + Z_-^2)}{DkT(Z_+ + Z_-)^2}$ and $m_+ = \frac{(Z_+ + Z_-)^2}{(Z_+^2 + Z_-^2)Z_+}$... (3)

TABLE I

Mean activity coefficients of KCl at 25°.

Conc.	Observed (molal).	Calculated (molar) ($a_+ = 2.76\text{\AA}$, $a_- = 1.81\text{\AA}$)		
		I	II	III
0.01	0.922*	0.8966	0.9243	0.9253
0.05	0.840*	0.7987	0.8472	0.8502
0.1	0.794*, 0.769	0.7408	0.7987	0.8046
0.5	0.682*, 0.650	0.5802	0.6521	0.6759
1	0.534*, 0.605	0.5091	0.5794	0.6222
2	0.575	0.4433	0.5091	0.5820
3	0.573	0.4087	0.4698	0.5701
4	0.582	0.3860	0.4433	0.5666

* Falkenhagen, "Electrolytes" (1934). All other values have been taken from Harned and Owen, "The Physical Chemistry of Electrolytic Solutions", (1943).

TABLE II

Mean activity coefficient of CsCl at 25°.

Conc.	Observed (molal)	Calculated ($a_+ = 1.67\text{\AA}$)		
		I	II	III
0.01	—	0.8950	0.9234	0.9241
0.05	—	0.7927	0.8435	0.8453
0.1	0.755	0.7307	0.7927	0.7956
0.5	0.664	0.5542	0.6339	0.6409
1	0.543	0.4742	0.5542	0.5699
2	0.495	0.3997	0.4742	0.5010
3	0.480	0.3603	0.4297	0.4671
4	0.474	0.3347	0.3996	0.4462

It will be seen that the agreement with the equation (III) is quite satisfactory. Still better agreement can be attained by properly choosing the ionic diameters. In the solution the ionic radius gives the average distance of closest approach between oppositely charged ions. The observed higher values may be explained by assuming that at higher concentrations ionic diameters increase somewhat due to hydration and also to the fact that the average distance of closest approach (between oppositely charged ions) become greater due to mutual repulsion of like charges. Moreover, the calculated values will give higher results if we take into account the change of dielectric constant with concentration. In addition, the effects of secondary forces, which have been neglected, should be considered at higher concentrations but their influence is to decrease the calculated values. All these factors give the resultant values observed. The data, however, show that these are really of secondary importance.

Tables III-V give the relevant data for the alkali halides. It will be seen that the deviations are greater at higher concentrations and they occur in the order $I^- > Br^- > Cl^-$. This is quite in order with the increased polarisability of the ions.

TABLE III

Mean activity coefficients at 25°.

Conc.	CsCl $a_+ = 1.67\text{Å}$ $a_- = 1.81\text{Å}$		RbCl $a_+ = 1.48\text{Å}$		KCl $a_+ = 1.33\text{Å}$		KCl $a_+ = 2.76\text{Å}$	NaCl $a_+ = 3.2\text{Å}$	
	obs.	Calc.	obs.	calc.	obs.	calc.	calc.	obs.	calc.
	(molal)	(molar)							
0.01	—	0.9239	—	0.9237	0.9221 0.899	—	0.9251	0.903 0.9221	0.9255
1.0	0.543	0.5690	0.583	0.5658	0.605 0.6341	0.5580	0.6222	0.658 0.6891	0.6483
4.0	0.474	0.4462	0.541	0.4292	0.581	0.4170	0.5666	0.792	0.6220

TABLE IV

Mean activity coefficients at 25°.

Conc.	CsBr $a_+ = 1.96\text{Å}$		RbBr		KBr $a_+ = 1.33\text{Å}$		KBr $a_+ = 2.76\text{Å}$	NaBr	
	Obs.	Calc.	obs.	calc.	obs.	calc.	calc.	obs.	calc.
	(molal)	(molar)							
0.01	—	0.9239	—	0.9239	—	—	0.9251	—	0.9258
1.0	0.537	0.5765	0.579	0.5723	0.617	0.5644	0.6296	0.687	0.6558
4.0	0.460	0.4614	0.517	0.4435	0.525	0.4307	0.5853	0.938	0.5425

TABLE V

Mean activity coefficients at 25°.

Conc.	CsI $a_+ = 2.19\text{Å}$		RbI		KI $a_+ = 1.33\text{Å}$		KI $a_+ = 2.76\text{Å}$	NaI	
	obs.	calc.	obs.	calc.	obs.	calc.	calc.	obs.	calc.
	(molal)	(molar)							
0.01	—	0.9241	—	0.9241	—	—	0.9253	—	0.9260
1.0	0.532	0.5865	0.575	0.5825	0.646	0.5744	0.6404	0.739	0.6673
4.0	—	0.4850	0.517	0.4665	0.678	0.4530	0.6159	—	0.6761

Again Debye's equation cannot offer any explanation for the values of activity coefficients being greater than unity, but the equation (III) may give such values at higher concentrations if the values of the ionic diameters are sufficiently large. Tables VI and VII and Figs. 3 and 4 show the values of RCl and RA where the ionic radii of R^+ and A^- have been taken to be $5.0\text{\AA}$. For comparison the observed values of activity coefficients of $NaCl$ and HCl have been included. The nature and slope of the curves show striking similarity.

FIG. 3

TABLE VI

Mean activity coefficients of RCl at 25°.

Conc.	Observed (molal) NaCl	Calculated (molal) ($\sigma_{R^+} = 5.0\text{\AA}$)		
		I	II	III
0.01	0.922*	0.8981	0.9260	0.9270
0.05	0.842*	0.8093	0.8535	0.8672
0.1	0.778, 0.798*	0.7575	0.8031	0.8345
0.5	0.682	0.6167	0.6792	0.7734
1.0	0.658	0.5546	0.6167	0.7716
2.0	0.671	0.4967	0.5549	0.7945
3.0	0.720	0.4659	0.5201	0.8215
4.0	0.792	0.4453	0.4968	0.8506

FIG. 4

TABLE VII

Mean activity coefficients of RA at 25°.

Conc.	Observed (molal) HCl.		Calculated average distance $t. \pm., a_{H^+} = a_{Cl^-} = 5.0 \text{ \AA}$		
			I	II	III
0.01	0.9048	0.9005	0.9285	0.9340	
0.05	0.8304	0.8254	0.8632	0.8894	
0.1	0.7964	0.7834	0.8254	0.8742	
0.5	0.7571	0.6816	0.7249	0.9247	
1.0	0.8090	0.6418	0.6813	1.035	
2.0	1.009	0.6071	0.6425	1.238	
3.0	1.316	0.5898	0.6112	1.410	
4.0	1.762	0.5788	0.6071	1.573	

For polyvalent electrolytes, however, the agreement is not so satisfactory. Tables VIII and IX and Figs. 5 and 6 record the values for BaCl_2 and LaCl_3 solutions. The crystallographic values of ionic diameters have been used. Here also equation (III)

FIG. 5

TABLE VIII

Mean activity coefficients of BaCl_2 at 25°.

Conc.	Observed (molal).	Calculated (molal) ($a_± = 1.31\text{Å}$).		
		I	II	III
0.01	0.723	0.6874	0.7521	0.8360
0.05	0.554	0.4652	0.5521	0.6923
0.1	0.492	0.3621	0.4495	0.6189
0.5	0.390	0.1641	0.2258	0.4224
1.0	0.392	0.1087	0.1545	0.3452
2.0	(1.8 → 0.450)	0.0711	0.1021	0.2823

FIG. 6

approximates more closely to the observed values. Below the normal concentration the calculated figures give higher values, while above it they are smaller than the observed ones. The higher values may possibly be due to the effects of secondary forces, e.g., forces of polarisation, forces of interaction between the solvent and the

TABLE IX

Mean activity coefficients of LaCl_3 at 25° .

Conc.	Observed (molal).	Calculated (molar) ($a_+ = 1.06\bar{a}$).		
		I	II	III
0.01	0.637	0.4567	0.5320	0.7630
0.05	0.447	0.2066	0.2737	0.5923
0.1	0.383	0.1254	0.1778	0.5124
0.5	0.328	0.0274	0.0446	0.3183
1.0	0.224	0.0070	0.0215	0.2557
2.0	(1.4 $\rightarrow$ 0.587)	0.0059	0.0057	0.2088

solute etc., which are likely to be of more importance for ions of higher valencies, being neglected. The deviation at higher concentrations may be ascribed, in addition to the effects of these secondary forces, to the factors mentioned above, notably due to the increased average distance between the ions caused by the repulsive forces of like charges of higher valencies and to the change in the dielectric constant at higher concentrations.

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